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Analysis of the relationship between communication management strategies and external crisis management strategies in large-scale contractor operations within the Sri Lankan construction industry

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The Sri Lankan Construction Industry (SLCI) faces significant challenges from external factors such as terrorism, natural disasters, economic and financial crises, political instability, and competition from foreign contractors. During crisis periods, a substantial amount of information is generated, and the resulting communication patterns can directly influence crisis management by creating conflicts and discouraging collective responsibility. The success or failure of crisis management heavily depends on communication management strategies. The scarcity of studies on external crisis management within the SLCI creates knowledge gaps and increases risks for the industry. Thus, the study is aimed to assess the relationship between Communication Management Strategies (CMS) and External Crisis Management Strategies (ECMS) in the SLCI to help construction organizations survive during external crises. An online questionnaire survey was conducted to collect quantitative data relevant to ECMS and CMS, involving 101 participants from the SLCI. The Pearson's correlation test was used to identify relationships between CMS and ECMS. The significance level (α) was less than 0.001, providing sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and demonstrating a significant linear relationship between ECMS and CMS. The Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was 0.454, indicating a moderate positive linear relationship between ECMS and CMS. This suggested that construction organizations could enhance the effectiveness of their external crisis management by applying appropriate CMS strategies. Effective communication channels and management structures are crucial for crisis preparedness and response. By focusing on these areas, the SLCI can better navigate the complexities of external crisis situations, maintaining stability and resilience. Robust communication systems ensure smooth and uninterrupted information flow, allowing construction organizations to respond quickly and effectively to crises. The intention of the outcomes of the study is to facilitate smoother operations during external crises in large-scale main contractor organizations registered under the Construction Contractors Grading Schema of the Construction Development Authority of Sri Lanka. Using insights from this research, construction organizations can implement strategic CMS to strengthen their ECMS, leading to more resilient and stable operations during external crises.

Keywords: External Crisis Management Strategies, Communication Management Strategies, Construction Industry, Large-Scale Contractor

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